

On the Control of Multi-Function Reprogrammable Silicon Chip for ROADMs and Sliceable Transceivers

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Abstract – This study investigates the use of a reconfigurable multi-functional reprogrammable silicon chip as an add/drop network device for a sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver. Software-Defined Networking (SDN) with NETCONF/YANG protocol is used for control and management, leveraging REST API to facilitate communication and coordination between the device local controller and the silicon chip-integrated device.
Keywords- Reprogrammable silicon chip, SDN control, NETCONF, YANG, REST API.

1. INTRODUCTION

The recent availability of off-the-shelf reprogrammable Photonic Integrated Circuits (PIC) [1] has the potential to revolutionize the way optical network elements are designed and implemented. In particular, reprogrammable PICs offer a cost-effective solution guaranteeing unprecedented flexibility and agile response to changing network demands. The primary advantage of this circuit rests on the flexibility to have full software enabled programming and control of the circuit.

In [2], we see an examination of how these generic chips can accelerate the development of future photonic circuits by providing a higher-level platform for prototyping novel optical functionalities without the need for custom chip fabrication. Additionally, according to [3], multipurpose programmable circuits promise to achieve arbitrary functionality and dynamic system operation as an alternative to custom fixed design. The work reviews the fundamentals, programming methods, and performance of its application to microwave-photonics and computing.

The overall, ultimate objective of this work is to design, implement and validate an SDN agent for the programmable PIC or photonic mesh, that can leverage the underlying device flexibility and applicability. In this line, this paper presents, first, the PIC macroscopic capabilities, our targeted deployment use cases, as well as the initial considerations in terms of abstraction and modelling and a preliminary architecture. Basic SDN architectural and protocol concepts are introduced, and different implementation options are discussed. We also identify two related use cases that benefit from a common framework development: the usage of the PIC as add/drop module in a ROADM architecture and as a combiner element for multiple optical flows/slices of a sliceable bandwidth variable transceiver (S-BVT).

2. PROGRAMMABLE PIC PLATFORM

iPronics waveguide mesh consists of multiple programmable unit cells (PUCs) based on 3-dB splitters and thermo-optic phase shifters connected together to create a hexagonal topology, as represented in *Figure 1*. This waveguide mesh arrangement enables a high set of applications, such as optical beam splitters/combiners or $N \times M$ optical switches. Moreover, the hexagonal topology also permits light recirculation, enabling the synthetization of different filters, such as asymmetric Mach-Zehnder interferometers (AMZI), optical ring resonators (ORR) or ring-assisted Mach-Zehnder interferometers (RAMZI) [3].

The photonic platform (developed for the EU ALLEGRO project) can work at dual polarization (TE and TM) thanks to the polarization beam splitters and combiners shown in figure 1. Furthermore, it also includes extra modules (high-performance blocks, HPB) that can be accessed from the mesh for dispersion compensation (lattice filter) or fiber interrogation (arrayed waveguide grating, AWG). The PUCs in the mesh are configured by the proprietary API.

Figure 1: Integrated photonic platform (left) based on Programmable Unit Cells (right)

3. PROPOSED REPROGRAMMABLE PIC-BASED NETWORK ELEMENTS

A. ADD/DROP MODULE

In this section, the iPronics PIC is considered as an innovative add/drop module of a multi-degree ROADM. This PIC

presents the unique capability to effectively implement the slice-ability concept, enabling different optical channels to be routed towards either common or different destinations in a flexible way. For example, with reference to the Figure 2, the channels entering/leaving the PIC could be all routed towards a single direction (e.g., West Port) or each towards independent ports (e.g., first channel to West, second and third channels to North). Programmable PIC-based Add/Drop modules have the potential to represent a more cost-effective technology compared to traditional solutions based on Wavelength Selective Switches (WSS).

To support such innovation, specific enhancements to the ROADM control are needed, thus, Yet Another Next-Generation (YANG) data modeling language, is utilized to provide a standardized method for monitoring and controlling the PIC module. The initial YANG model may include elements for managing channels and wavelength selection, performance monitoring, and capabilities for dynamic reconfiguration and automation. The SDN controller uses the NETCONF protocol for communication with the agent, which leverages REST API for the actual device monitoring and configuration.

Figure 2: IPRONICS PIC used as ADD/DROP module in a ROADM architecture with enhanced OpenROADM/OpenConfig control

B. AGGREGATOR/DISTRIBUTOR MODULE OF A S-BVT

Smart sliceable transceivers, such as the S-BVT, support flexible multi-rate, multi-flow, multi-format, and multi-reach transmission [4]. The aggregation/distribution of the multiple flows (or slices) from/to the multiple BVT modules composing the S-BVT is performed by using the photonic waveguide mesh (WGM) based PIC as a data plane element. Both the S-BVT and the WGM are programmable (SDN-enabled), and for a targeted multi-flow signal generation, aggregation, distribution, and reception, the SDN controller configures/programs: i) the S-BVT transmitter/receiver (Tx/Rx) elements; and ii) the optical circuit of WGM. The generic SDN-controlled photonic architecture is shown in Figure 3(a). The data plane elements are controlled by the SDN controller via specific SDN agents. The identification of attributes that are susceptible to be programmed and their proper modelling, in accordance with the intended architecture and the actual technologies, defines the first step towards the development of SDN agents for the data plane elements. YANG data modeling language is used to provide a standard way to describe the data plane elements to be monitored and controlled [5]. In the YANG model, specific attributes of the S-BVT include enabling/disabling the BVT modules and setting the parameters of adaptive DSP (operational mode, modulation format, FEC, target BER) of each enabled BVT. For WGM function as an aggregator, the YANG model includes connect/disconnect, state information, reset, and combiner attributes. The SDN controller-agent communication relies on the REST-API to actually apply/read a specific configuration/state. Figure 3(b) shows the implementation of SDN controller and agent workflow adopting the REST-API GET and POST methods for monitoring and configuration of defined S-BVT and WGM elements.

Figure 3: SDN Controlled Photonic System. (a) SDN controller-agents architecture and S-BVT based photonic system; (b) REST-API Workflow for monitoring and configuring the SDN Agents.

4. PROPOSED CONTROL ARCHITECTURE

A REST API interface is used by a NETCONF Agent to configure and collect monitored parameters from the underlying hardware, which in this work is considered as the emulated device. Additionally, a preliminary YANG model is being developed to enable the SDN control of the reconfigurable PIC. The device is based on the iPrronics SDK with a Python program layer for interactions with the SDN controller. In Figure 4 we propose an architecture to be used in the control plane for the proposed device. The NETCONF protocol interfaces with the SDN agent, and the southbound interface liaises with the device in the data plane via the REST API.

Figure 4: Proposed SDN Agent architecture

REQUIREMENTS (PROTOCOLS AND IMPLEMENTATION OPTIONS):

Regarding the implementation, the SDN controller option in evaluation for this work relies on the NETCONF protocol. In the implementation of the SDN controller, factors to influence the features of the proposed SDN agent include:

- **Open Interface:** The SDN agent should provide an open, standardized interface for communication with network management and control systems to advance interoperability and integration with existing SDN controllers and orchestrators.
- **Real-time Control:** The SDN agent must be capable of real-time control and reconfiguration of PICs to respond promptly to changing network conditions and service demands.
- **Scalability:** It should support fine-tuned control over individual optical channels or components within PICs, while also being scalable to large-scale network deployments with numerous nodes and links.
- **Reliability:** This proposed SDN agent should be robust and reliable, capable of handling failures or errors gracefully without compromising active network performances or stability.

PROPRIETARY API:

The emulated device (waveguide mesh) in the data plane is configured by a high-level proprietary API designed by iPrronics. As presented earlier in Section 2 of this paper, the waveguide mesh is made up of multiple PUCs. Each of these PUCs are configured to set the required parameters of the photonic waveguide mesh. The waveguide mesh of the emulated device is built using this high-level API's commands as presented in the table below.

Table 1: High-level Proprietary API.

Configuration parameters	High-level Proprietary API	
Connecting the PIC hardware	<code>def connect()</code>	Connects the hardware subsystems and gets the system ready for configurations.
Set the PUCs state	<code>def set_puc_states()</code>	Sets the states for specified PUCs.
Function of the PUCs in the mesh based on the input port and output port.	<code>def interconnect()</code>	Creates a circuit connection between the specified input and output port of the mesh.
	<code>def beamsplitter()</code>	Creates a splitter between the given mesh input port and output ports.
	<code>def combiner()</code>	Creates a combiner between the given mesh input ports and output port.
	<code>def switch()</code>	Create a switch between the given mesh inputs and outputs.
	<code>def compensate_dispersion()</code>	Compensates for the dispersion slope for the specified central wavelength and bandwidth.
Deactivate active PUCs in the mesh	<code>def reset()</code>	Sets the control signal of the PUCs to the default state.
Disconnect the PIC hardware	<code>def disconnect()</code>	Disconnects the hardware subsystems.

In the beamsplitter function, the optical power is divided equally and in the combiner function, optical power combined with equal ratio of the input port signals. Additionally, this high-level API also allows for the monitoring of parameters such as the PUC state, the input and output power in each port and the temperature of the PIC. The Rest API is employed to mediate between the high-level proprietary API and the SDN agent in the control plane to facilitate the configuration and monitoring of the emulated device.

The following advantages are added by the proposed control architecture for the use cases:

- Flexible channel provisioning: The flexibility is to enable efficient resource allocation and channel provisioning for network.
- Wavelength/Channel Path protection: In case of network failures or fibre cuts, the emulated device module can be used to reroute affected wavelengths onto alternate paths to maintain service continuity. This capability enhances network resilience and ensures high availability of critical services.
- Reduced space and power consumption: The proposed module offers a more compact and power efficient architecture by integrating multiple functions unto a chip and thereby reduces energy consumption and physical space.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes some use cases for a PIC-module and presents the High-level proprietary API for building the SDN controlled photonic architecture. Future work is to design and implement the proposed system on the PIC hardware with the proposed SDN agents.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. L. Hernández, D. P. López, P. DasMahapatra and J. Capmany, "Dynamic reconfiguration in field-programmable photonic arrays," 45th European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC 2019), Dublin, Ireland, 2019, pp. 1-3, DOI: 10.1049/cp.2019.1125.
- [2] W. Bogaerts, D. Pérez, J. Capmany, D. A. B. Miller, J. Poon, D. Englund, F. Morichetti and A. Melloni, "Programmable photonic circuits," Nature 586, 2020, pp. 207-216. DOI: 10.1038/s41586-020-2764-0
- [3] D. Pérez-López, "Large-scale Programmable Integrated Photonic Circuits: From Microwave Photonics to Optical Computing," 2022 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC), San Diego, CA, USA, 2022.
- [4] M. Svaluto Moreolo et al., "Programmable VCSEL-based photonic system architecture for future agile Tb/s metro networks," in Journal of Optical Communications and Networking, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. A187-A199, February 2021, Doi: 10.1364/JOCN.411964.
- [5] M. Svaluto Moreolo et al., "Demonstration of an SDN-enabled VCSEL-based Photonic System for Spectral/Spatial Connectivity in Disaggregated Optical Metro Networks," 2021 Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC), San Francisco, CA, USA, 2021, pp. 1-3.